

Report: Mealy Amazon (*Amazona farinosa*) counting in Ilhabela: April 2025 and beyond

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Introduction

The mealy amazon (*Amazona farinosa* Linnaeus, 1758) is one of the largest parrot species in the Neotropical region (fig.1) (Juniper & Parr, 1998; Collar et al., 2022). Its distribution extends from southern Mexico to the Brazilian Atlantic Forest, occupying a variety of tropical and subtropical forest habitats. In Brazil, populations have become increasingly fragmented due to deforestation, selective logging, and the illegal pet trade (Fortaleza, 1990).

Figure 1. Mealy parrot (*Amazona farinosa*) – Borrifos, south Ilhabela (Marcio Motta, 2025)

This species is categorized as Near Threatened globally by the IUCN (BirdLife International, 2016) and Vulnerable on the São Paulo State Red List (São Paulo, 2018). The decline of *A. farinosa* populations is particularly concerning because of its key ecological role as a large-

seed disperser—a process critical for maintaining the structure and regeneration of tropical forests. As a canopy-dwelling species that relies on mature trees for nesting and feeding, *A. farinosa* is especially sensitive to habitat fragmentation and forest degradation (Collar et al., 2022).

The island of Ilhabela, located on the northern coast of São Paulo State, provides an important refuge for this species (fig.2). With a total area of approximately 348 km², Ilhabela is composed of 13 islands and islets, with 85% of its territory protected under the Ilhabela State Park (Parque Estadual de Ilhabela – PEIb). Created in 1977, the park preserves over 27,000 hectares of well-conserved Atlantic Forest, ranging from sea level to over 1,300 meters in altitude. Its steep slopes, high humidity, and diverse vegetation types—from restinga to montane forest—offer rich feeding and nesting opportunities for parrots and other forest-dependent birds (Fundação Florestal 2015).

Figure 2. Map of location of Ilhabela’s Archipelago, southeast Brazil.

Ilhabela’s relatively isolated geography has also limited some anthropogenic pressures, allowing certain wildlife populations to persist in more stable conditions compared to mainland environments. Given its ecological importance, Ilhabela represents a natural laboratory for biodiversity monitoring and conservation initiatives.

This population counting of *A. farinosa* in Ilhabela, coordinated by the Área de Soltura Monitorada Cambaquara, seeks to establish a long-term monitoring baseline and to encourage community participation in conservation.

Objective

To estimate the local abundance, spatial distribution, and relative density of *Amazona farinosa* in Ilhabela through standardized counting methods, while building a collaborative framework for ongoing monitoring and conservation within the Ilhabela State Park and surrounding areas.

Methodology

The collaborative counting was conducted on April 12 and 13, 2025, under the coordination of the ASM Cambaquara in partnership with, World Parrot Trust, VIVA Instituto Verde Azul, Ilhabela State Park (PEIb), Ayrulus Expeditions, Municipality of Ilhabela, with participation from local volunteers and ornithologists. Previous studies on psittacids were reviewed to identify and select the methodological approach most appropriate for the objectives of the present study (Galetti et al., 2006; Nunes & Galetti, 2007; Scherer-Neto et al., 2019).

A total of 26 fixed sampling points were distributed across the island, covering northern, central, and southern sectors and representing different habitat types (primary and secondary forest, coastal slopes, and rural areas), as presented in fig. 3. Due to individual characteristics and the availability of each participant at the different sampling points, some points collected data on only one of the census days.

Figure 3. Points of counting.

Two daily sessions were conducted at each point:

- Afternoon session (16:00–18:00): coinciding with the species’ return to roosts.
- Morning session (06:00–08:00): corresponding to peak feeding and calling activity.

Observers recorded all visual and acoustic detections of *A. farinosa* for two hour per session, including the number of individuals, direction of flight, and behavior (e.g., feeding, flying, perched). To minimize double-counting, the data analysis incorporated three complementary filters to ensure accuracy in population estimation, recommended by Bibby et al. (2000) and Ralph et al. (1995) for avian point counts. Temporal grouping was applied by organizing observations into 10-minute intervals, minimizing the risk of counting the same individuals multiple times within a short time span. Spatial grouping was used to merge records from points located within a 2-kilometer radius, under the assumption that these may represent observations of the same flock moving across nearby areas. Finally, flight direction was considered: observations of birds flying in opposite directions (for example, north–south versus south–north) were treated as distinct events, preventing the artificial merging of separate groups. Together, these procedures produced a minimum detectable abundance, offering a conservative estimate of the population and reducing the likelihood of overestimation.

Results

The raw counting data, uncorrected for possible recounts, indicated a total of 2,065 individual observations over the two survey sessions. Twenty-one counting points were sampled on 12 April, and twenty were sampled on 13 April. On April 12, 2025 (afternoon), a total of 691 individuals were recorded, while on April 13, 2025 (morning), 1,374 individuals were observed across the sampling points (fig.4). After applying the conservative correction criteria—considering temporal grouping (10-minute intervals), spatial grouping (points within 2 km), and flight direction filtering—the adjusted estimates indicated 145 individuals for the afternoon session and 201 individuals for the morning session.

Figure 4. Count by points over the two days (North-South order).

Following the methodology proposed, the highest value obtained among the sessions was adopted as the minimum abundance estimate for the surveyed population, resulting in a conservative estimate of 201 individuals of *A. farinosa* in Ilhabela in that moment.

Discussion

The estimated 201 individuals suggest that Ilhabela supports a small but significant population of *A. farinosa*, consistent with its ecological requirements for extensive mature forest and fruit availability. The relatively higher count recorded during the morning session (April 13)

likely reflects the species' peak activity period, when parrots leave roosting sites in search of food, resulting in increased detectability.

From a conservation standpoint, these results underscore Ilhabela's role as an important refuge for forest-dependent psittacids. The persistence of the Mealy Amazon within the island's forests demonstrates that the protected areas—particularly the Ilhabela State Park (PEIb)—continue to provide suitable habitat conditions for breeding and foraging. However, the modest population size also indicates potential vulnerability to local disturbances, such as habitat fragmentation, illegal wildlife capture, and human encroachment in forest edges.

The data emphasize the necessity of long-term monitoring to detect demographic changes over time. Given that parrot populations can fluctuate seasonally in response to fruiting cycles and climatic factors, it is recommended to perform at least one census per season. This temporal replication will enable the identification of trends, such as recruitment, mortality, or migratory movements between sectors of the island.

Furthermore, the success of this counting illustrates the value of collaborative monitoring, involving local institutions, volunteers, and researchers (fig.5 and 6). The participation of citizens, local NGOs, park staff, and researchers created a multidisciplinary and community-based model of biodiversity monitoring. This participatory structure enhances both data quality and conservation impact, fostering a sense of shared responsibility for Ilhabela's natural heritage. To strengthen these efforts, it is recommended that future monitoring be carried out seasonally, with at least one census per season (four times per year). This would help identify potential fluctuations linked to breeding periods, fruit availability, and climatic variability. Regular, repeated censuses will also allow for the detection of long-term trends and the assessment of the effectiveness of conservation measures.

Fig. 5. A total of 32 volunteers participated of this edition of counting.

In the future, the integration of spatial data (GPS coordinates, habitat types, fruiting tree distribution) and acoustic monitoring could further improve the precision of population estimates. Coupling citizen science with technological tools (e.g., mobile apps, sound recorders, and mapping platforms) can expand both participation and scientific rigor. Ilhabela's ongoing efforts demonstrate that local conservation actions, when embedded within participatory frameworks, can provide valuable data for national and global conservation programs—particularly those focusing on threatened Neotropical parrots.

Figure 6. Celebration with the volunteers after the last day of the countings.

Next Step: **Monitoring of the species at the VIVA Instituto Verde Azul headquarters**

After the collective count in April, the event coordinator, Silvana Davino, invited biologist Dr. Marcio Motta, coordinator of the Environmental Education program and bird studies at VIVA Instituto Verde Azul, to initiate periodic monitoring of the species at the institute's headquarters, located in the southern part of Ilhabela, which was the southernmost point of the collective count. The institute's observation tower, used mainly for daily cetacean monitoring, is situated at approximately 100 meters above sea level and is located in an area adjacent to the boundaries of Ilhabela State Park (fig.7).

Since May, data collection takes place at least twice a month, from 16:00 to 18:00, during which the same information recorded in the collective count is collected, with the addition of sound recordings using a recorder and microphone. The initial proposal is to carry out this monitoring over the course of one year.

Figure 7. Tower of observation at VIVA Instituto Verde Azul, where the monitoring is being conducted.

Citizen Science – Collection Project on iNaturalist

To better understand the distribution of records of the species along the coastal region of São Paulo, a Collection Project was created on the citizen science platform iNaturalist (<https://www.inaturalist.org/projects/papagaio-moleiro-no-litoral-paulista>). Up to the present moment (November 2025), there are 208 records, 38 identifiers, and 51 observers contributing to the project (fig. 8). The records within the study area are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 8. Screenshot of the front page of the project on iNaturalist.

Figure 9. Distribution map of observations of the specie in the coast of Sao Paulo, Brazil.

Recommendations for Future Collaborative Monitoring

1. **Seasonal Counts:** Conduct standardized censuses at least once per season (four per year) to capture temporal variations and breeding cycles. Suggested months: January, April, July, and October.
2. **Team Structure:** Each session should include at least one trained observer and one assistant for data entry, ensuring coverage of all fixed points.
3. **Georeferenced Data:** Continue recording latitude and longitude at each observation point and associate them with habitat descriptors (vegetation type, elevation, proximity to forest edges).
4. **Acoustic Support:** Deploy sound recorders (e.g., Tascam H5n, Song Meter) in strategic locations to capture vocal activity, especially during dawn and dusk, to complement visual counts.
5. **Community Engagement:** Encourage the participation of local schools and residents through educational outreach and citizen science initiatives.
6. **Data Management:** Store all observations in a shared database (e.g., eBird or a local online platform) to facilitate transparency, replication, and long-term analysis.
7. **Long-Term Goal:** Establish a regional monitoring network for *Amazona farinosa* across the northern coast of São Paulo, integrating data from other municipalities to track metapopulation dynamics.

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